

THE ROLE OF KOSHITA IN OPTIMIZING DOSE FIXATION FOR VIRECHANA KARMA

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ABSTRACT

Virechana Karma, a key purification therapy in Ayurveda, is primarily aimed at eliminating the vitiated *Pitta Dosha*, and cleansing the body. A critical factor influencing the success of *Virechana* is the assessment of *Koshita*- an evaluation of an individual's digestive strength and bowel response. *Koshita* is categorized into three types: *Mrudu* (soft) *Madhyama* (moderate), and *Krura* (hard), and each type necessitates a customized approach in determining the correct dosage to achieve optimal therapeutic results. This article delves into the significance of *Koshita* assessment within the broader context of *Panchakarma*, examining how it guides the selection and administration of purgative medications used in *Virechana*. It outlines the scientific rationale behind *Koshita* evaluation, explores the various factors that influence a person's response to purgation, and discusses strategies for accurate dose determination. Recognizing these *Koshita* distinctions allows practitioners to individualize *Virechana Karma* to everyone, thereby

promoting safe, effective, and well-balanced purification. The article integrates traditional Ayurvedic knowledge with contemporary clinical understanding, emphasizing the need for accurate dosage to prevent complications like *Atiyoga* (excessive purgation) and *Ayoga*

(inadequate purgation). The objective is to emphasize the importance of accurate dosage based on *Koshta* assessment to ensure the safe and effective administration of *Virechana Karma*.

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, the concept of *Koshta* plays a significant role in understanding individual variations in digestion and excretion. Structurally, *Koshta* refers to the internal pathway of the gastrointestinal system, encompassing organs such as stomach, intestines, and associated channels responsible for the transformation and elimination of food. It serves as the primary site where digestion, absorption, and waste expulsion. The configuration and responsiveness of the *Koshta* differ from person to person, largely influenced by the predominance of *Doshas-Vata, Pitta* and *Kapha*. Functionally it can be classified into: *Mrudu, Madhyama, and Krura*, reflecting the speed and ease of digestive processes. A clear understanding of the structural and functional characteristics of *Koshta* is essential for fine-tuning effective Ayurvedic treatments and dietary recommendations.

Virechana is a therapeutic procedure in which orally administered medicines work to eliminate imbalanced *Doshas*, particularly targeting *Pitta Dosha*, and expel them through the anal pathway. *Virechana Karma* is not limited to *Pitta* alone; it is also effective in managing conditions involving *Pitta* combined with *Vata* or *Kapha*. *Virechana* can also be defined as the process of elimination of *Mala* either in *Pakwa* or in *Apakwa Avastha* but along with excessive fluid portion is known as *Virechana*.^[1]

IMPORTANCE OF KOSHTA ASSESSMENT

1. As predicting or prognostic value.
 - *Udavarta* can occur in patients of *Vata* dominant *Koshta*. The patients of *Krura Koshta* are prone to have *Udavarta* with or without the occurrence of *Arshas*.^[2]
2. To decide the course of Panchakarma
 - Patients who are *Ruksha*, having *Vata Prakopa*, *Krura Koshta*, *Vyayama Sheelina*, *Deepthagni* if administered *Virechana* medicine may not give desired result. So before giving *Virechana* medicine it is ideal to administer *Basti*, *Snigdha Virechana*, or *Teeksna Phala Varti*.^[3]

3. To select ideal drugs for Panchakarma
 - In *Sukumara, Shishu, Vruddha, Mrudu Koshta* people *Trivruth* is drug of choice for *Virechana*.^[4]
4. To assess *Vyapat*
 - If a *Mrudu Koshta* person is administered with *Tikshna Ausadha*, it results in *Vyapat*. To prevent this *Koshta* assessment is mandatory.^[5]

CLASSIFICATION OF KOSHITA

1. Based on predominance of Dosha^[6]

Koshta can be categorized into three: *Krura, Madhyama, Mrudu*

- *Mrudu Koshta* is typically influenced by an excess of *Pitta* and are easily evacuated, often facilitated by substances like milk.
- *Krura Koshta* usually indicate predominance of *Vata* and *Kapha* and are purgated with difficulty. Even with the use of drugs like *Shyama*, purgation is difficult to achieve.^[7]
- *Madhyama Koshta* have balanced *Doshas* and respond moderately to purgation.

In the context of *Vamana*, Hemadiri classified *Koshta* as^[8]

Shleshmadhikyane- Mrudu Koshta

Shleshmamadhyatwane- Madhya Koshta

Shleshmaheenatwane- Krura Koshta

TYPE OF KOSHITA AND DOSHA PREDOMINANCE

Table 1

Type of <i>Koshta</i>	Charaka	Susrutha	Vagbhata	Vangasena	Sarangadhara
<i>Mrudu</i>	<i>Udirna Pitta Alpa Kapha</i>	<i>Bahu Pitta</i>	<i>Bahu Pitta</i>	<i>Pittadhiko</i>	<i>Pitta</i>
<i>Madhyama</i>		<i>Samadosha</i>		<i>Samadosha</i>	<i>Kapha, Samadosha</i>
<i>Krura</i>	<i>Atyulbana Anila</i>	<i>BahuVata Sleshma</i>	<i>Prabhuta Maruta</i>	<i>Vatena Sleshmana</i>	<i>Vata</i>

2. Based on duration to attain *Snigdhattha*^[9]

- *Krura Koshta*: Person attain *Snigdhattha* in 7 days
- *Madhyama Koshta*: Person attain *Snigdhattha* in 5 days
- *Mrudu Koshta*: Person attain *Snigdhattha* in 3 days

According to Dalhana, based on duration of *Snehana*,^[10]

Table 2

Type of <i>Koshta</i>	Duration (In days)
<i>Mrudu Tama</i>	1
<i>Mrudu Tara</i>	2
<i>Mrudu</i>	3
<i>Madhyama Tara</i>	4
<i>Madhyama Tama</i>	5
<i>Madhyama</i>	6
<i>Krura</i>	7
<i>Krura Tara</i>	8
<i>Krura Tama</i>	9

Achyarya Charaka classified *Koshta* based on the intake of *Dravyas*^[11]

Table 3

<i>Mrudu Koshta</i> : <i>Pitta</i> is more, <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i> are less, hence purgation is easy.	People with <i>Mrudu Koshta</i> undergo <i>Virechana</i> effectively with the following substances like <i>Guda</i> (jaggery), <i>Ikshu Rasa</i> (sugarcane juice), <i>Mastu</i> (whey), <i>Kshira</i> (milk), <i>Ullodita</i> (milk cream from curd), <i>Dadhi</i> (curd), <i>Krushara</i> (gruel made from sesame, rice, and black gram) <i>Sarpi</i> (ghee), <i>Kashmarya Rasa</i> , <i>Triphala Rasa</i> , <i>Draksha Rasa</i> and <i>Pilu Rasa</i> , <i>Ushna Jala</i> , <i>Taruna Madhya</i> (fresh wine).
<i>Krura Koshta</i> : Primarily influenced by <i>Vata Dosha</i> .	Substances are ineffective in individuals with <i>Krura Koshta</i> , where the <i>Grahani</i> receives only partially digested food.

According to Charaka Kalpasthana^[12]

- *Trivrit* is *Kashaya Madhura* in *Rasa*, *Rooksha* and *Katu Vipaka*. It is *Kapha Pitta hara*. It is of two types-*Syama* and *Aruna*. *Aruna Trivrit* is more useful.
- *Aruna Trivrit* is useful for *Sukumara* persons, *Shishu*, *Vridha* and *Mrudu Koshta*.
- *Syama Trivrit* is more *Teekshana*, and is useful in *Bahu dosha* and *Krura Koshta*
- *Chaturangula Kalpa* is *Mrudu* in nature. So, it can be given in *Bala*, *Vridha*, *Kshata Kshina*, *Sukumara*.
- *Sudha* is *Teekshna* among *Virechana Dravyas*. So, it is not advised in patient having *Mrudu Koshta*, and when there is less accumulation of *Doshas* and when alternative therapeutic measures are available for managing the disease.

According to Hemadri, based on response to *Shodhana*^[13]

3. If, after administering a moderate dose of *Sodhana*, signs of *Hina Yoga* are observed, the *Koshta* is considered *Krura*.

If *Ati-yoga* occurs, the *Koshta* is identified as *Mrdu*.

When *Samyak Yoga* is attained, it indicates a *Madhyama Koshta*.

DOSE OF VIRECHANA DRAVYA BASED ON KOSHITA

Table 4

KOSHITA	DOSE	ANUPANA	DOSE
<i>Mrudu</i>	1 Karsha	<i>Ushnodaka</i>	1 Pala
<i>Madhyama</i>	Ardha Pala	<i>Ushnodaka</i>	2 Pala
<i>Krura</i>	1 Pala	<i>Ushnodaka</i>	3 Pala

According to Sarangadhara, *Virechana Vidhi*,^[14]

Table 5

Koshita	Mrudu	Madhyama	Krura
Dosha dominance	<i>Bahu Pitta</i>	<i>Bahu Sleshma</i>	<i>Prabhoota Maruta</i>
Rasa	<i>Kashaya, Madhura</i>	<i>Katuka</i>	<i>Snigdha, Ushna Lavana</i>
Dosage	<i>Alpa</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Pravara</i>
<i>Virechana Dravya</i>	<i>Draksa Payas, Ambu, Taila</i>	<i>Trivrit, Kiratatikta, Rajavrksa</i>	<i>Snuhi Ksheera, Swarnaksheeri, Danti phala</i>

Dose of various *Virechana yogas*,^[15]

Table 6

Formulations	Maximum Dose	Medium Dose	Maximum Dose
<i>Kwatha</i>	2 Pala	1 Pala	½ Pala
<i>Kalka</i>	1 Pala	2 Karsha	1 Karsha
<i>Modaka</i>	1 Pala	2 Karsha	1 Karsha
<i>Churna</i>	1 Pala	2 Karsha	1 Karsha

Based on *Dosha* predominance^[16]

Table 7

DOSHA PREDOMINANCE	VIRECHANA YOGAS
<i>PITTAJA ROGAS</i>	<i>Trivrit churna with Draksha Kwatha</i>
<i>KAPHAJA ROGAS</i>	<i>Triphala Kwatha mixed with Gomutra, Trikatu Churna</i>
<i>VATAJA ROGAS</i>	<i>Trivrit Churna, Saindhava Lavana, Sunthi Churna along with Amla Dravya or Jangala Mamsa Rasa.</i>

According to *Cakradutta Virechana adhikara*,^[17]

Based on *Doshas* the *Rasa* to be chosen is mentioned.

Table 8

<i>Pitta</i>	<i>Kashaya Madhura</i>
<i>Kapha</i>	<i>Katu</i>
<i>Vata</i>	<i>Snigdha, Ushna, Lavana</i>

Asnigdha Koshtasya PunarVirechanam- If a person is not uncted well, he should be given *Virechana Dravya* after 10 days after preparing his body well with unction and sudation keeping in mind the previous performance.^[18]

- **Aparinjatha Koshta**- One who is *Durbala, Shodhita, Poorvamalapa Dosha, Krsa, Aparinjatha Koshta* take medicine in mild and small dose.^[19]
- **Rookshadhi Koshta**- Patient with *Rooksha, Bahu Anila, Krura Koshta, Vyayama Sevina, Deeptagni* drug is digested without exerting purgative action. In such case first enema should be given then *Snigdha Virechana*.^[20]
- **Snigdha -Rooksha Virechanam** -In *Asnigdha* person *Snigdha Virechanam* should be done and in *Atisnigdha* person *Rooksha Virechanam* should be done. The person who is *Sneha Satmya Rookshana* is done first and then *Snigdha Virechana* is advised.^[21]

In Kashyapa Samhita causes of various complications while using emetics and purgatives and their treatment has been explained. In that context Acharya has explained, if *Krura Koshta* person not given *Snehana* properly, use of *Alpa* or *Mrudu Aushada* result in complications like *Pratishyaya, Anaha, Kapha Praseka*.

If a person with *Mrudu Koshta* even after proper *Snehana* and *Swedana* if given *Bahu Aushadha* that *Aushadha* becomes cause for discharge of vital blood. Vata gets aggravated cause *Pralepa, Unmada, Hikka Swasa, Kasa, Talu Shosha, Trshna, Shoola Badirya, Vakgraha Beejopaghta, Timira, Pushpopaghata*.^[22]

Practical assessment of *Koshta* can be done through various parameters.^[23]

Table 9

PARAMETER	MRUDU KOSHTA	MADHYAMA KOSHTA	KRURA KOSHTA
BOWEL HABIT	Regular daily 1-2 times	Regular daily once	Irregular(constipated)
STOOL CONSISTENCY	Semi solid/formed	Formed	Hard, dry
TIME AND STRESS FOR DEFECATION	Minimum time required for defecation with ease	Little long time required with usual strain	Requires a long time and straining
PREVIOUS ENCOUNTER OF DIARRHOEA/CONSTIPATION	Often loose stool with hot drinks, milk	Rarely	Seldom encounters diarrhoea, more frequent constipation
USUAL DOSE REQUIRED FOR PURGATION	Minor laxative	Medium dose	Drastic purgative

For clinical evaluation of *Koshta*:

Frequency per day: Less than one-1

Once/twice-2

More than 2-3

Consistency: Hard stool-1

Soft well-formed -2

Loose/watery and not well formed-3

Urgency: No urgency at all, sits long time with discomfort-1

Moderate urgency, can be controlled but no need to sit long-2

Marked urgency cannot be controlled-3

Based on the experience regarding intake of 200 ml milk/100 g grapes/50 g jaggery/200 ml sugarcane juice/10 g *Avipattikara Churna*

No change in bowel habit-1

Normal well-formed stool-2

Watery stool/not well formed-3

Whether changes in food habits will affect your bowel habits frequently

No change in bowel habit-1

Occasionally-2

Frequent loose-3

SCORE

Table 10

1-5	Krura <i>Koshta</i>
6-10	Madhyama <i>Koshta</i>
11-15	Mrudu <i>Koshta</i>

The *Koshta* Deciding Scale is a valuable tool for determining an individual's *Koshta*. It offers a clear practical method for assessing this aspect, aiding the Vaidya in selecting appropriate type and dosage of medicines, particularly in the context of *Shodhana Chikitsa*. 100 patients were selected and a Clinical Performa was prepared based on 6 major parameters. A detailed questionnaire was prepared to assess the parameters clearly to avoid any ambiguity. Its usefulness extends beyond *Shodhana*, playing an important role in *Shamana Chikitsa* as well, where accurate determination of medicine type and quantity is essential.

Koshta Deciding Scale (KDS)^[24]

Table 11

Sl. No	Parameters	Mrudu ^[33]	Madhya ^[15]	Krura ^[33]
1	Frequency and consistency of stool	Unformed 1-4 times a day ^[7]	Formed and soft 1-2 times a day ^[3]	Formed and hard Alternate day or more

				than that ^[7]
2	Effect of taking hot milk, hot water etc at night	Every time watery loose stool and frequent ^[7]	No effect of these food products and no need of laxatives ^[3]	No effect even after use of mild laxatives ^[7]
3	Passing of stool (usually)	Without any efforts very easily and satisfactory ^[7]	With normal efforts and satisfactory ^[3]	With more efforts and unsatisfactory ^[7]
4	Time taken for defecation (excluding the time for newspaper, mobile, reading)	1-4 min ^[5]	5-10 min ^[3]	More than 10 min ^[5]
5	Feeling of urge for defecation	Feeling of urge as wake up in the morning ^[7]	Feeling of urge within 20 min of waking up ^[3]	No feeling of urge and needs to take some articles like hot water, tea etc ^[7]
6	H/O diseases related to stools	-	-	H/O Haemorrhoids, Fissure, Fistula ^[3]
	Total score			

The questionnaire was developed based on textual references and observation expressed by various authors. To decide the nature of *Koshta* practically, help of textual references of reaction of laxatives and influence of *Doshas* on *Koshta* was taken to decide parameters for *Koshta* analysis.

Decision of the nature of *Koshta* based on KDS-

1. When the KDS for Mrudu *Koshta* is 12
2. or more than 12 when the scores of *Krura* and *Madhyama* are below 12, the *Koshta* is said to be *Mrudu*.
3. When the KDS for *Madhyama Koshta* is 9 or more than 9 when the other two are below
4. 9, then the *Koshta* is said to be *Madhyama*.
5. When the KDS for *Krura Koshta* is 12 or more than 12 when the scores of *Mrudu* and *Madhyama* are below 12, the *Koshta* is said to be *Krura*.

DISCUSSION

Koshta assessment holds a pivotal role in Panchakarma, serving as a predictive tool for both disease susceptibility and therapeutic planning. By evaluating the *Koshta*, the predominance of *Doshas* can be understood, which in turn guides the appropriate *Shodhana* procedure. Drug selection in Panchakarma is also influenced by *Koshta* type-for instance, *Snigdha Virechana* or *Ruksha Virechana* may be chosen accordingly. In *Ruksha*, *Bahu-Anila*, *Krura*

Koshta individuals with *Deepthagni*, if *Virechana* is administered without proper *Koshta* evaluation, the medicine may be digested without inducing purgation. In such situations *Basti* or *Tikshna Phala Varti* may be administered to expel stool. For individuals with *Mandagni* and *Krura koshta* administration of *Sakshara Lavana Ghrita* as a preparatory measure supports proper stimulation of *Agni* and balancing of *Kapha Vat*.^[25]

In *Krimi Koshta*, *Vata Vyadhi*, *Pravrudha Kapha Medas*, who needs *Drudatha* and in *Taila Satmya* should be chosen for *Snehapana*. Hence based on *Koshta* the drug of choice can be determined.^[26]

Importantly, *Koshta* examination is essential in preventing *Vyapats*. In a *Mridu Koshta* individual with *Laghu Doshavastha*, administration of *Ati-Tikshna Aushadha*, after elimination of *Doshas*, may lead to complication resulting in bleeding that can even prove fatal.^[27]

According to Acharya *Vagbhata* *Virechana* is contraindicated in individuals with *Krura Koshta*, as it may lead to excessive provocation of *Doshas* resulting in complications such as *Hridayashoola*, *Parvabhedha*, *Anaha*, *Chardhi*, *Murcha*, *Klama* and may even become life threatening.^[28]

Thus, a systematic assessment of *Koshta* not only aids in deciding treatment strategies but also ensures precautionary measures for safe and effective panchakarma practice.

Dose fixation is highly essential, as it must always be assessed carefully. In individuals who are *Durbala*, *Shodita* with *Alpa Dosha*, *Krsa Nara*, or with *Aparijnata Koshta*, smaller dose of medicine should be administered. If there is doubt, it is advisable to give the drug in repeated smaller doses rather than in a single large quantity.^[29]

Administering a large dose of *Tikshna Ausadha* may adversely affect *Prana*. On the other hand, repeated smaller doses help in eliminating *Bahu Dosha* gradually, without causing *Balahani* to the patient, while still ensuring effective removal of the aggravated *Doshas*.

The benefits of *Sodhana* therapy include *Buddhi Prasada*, *Bala Indriyanam*, *Dhathu sthiratva*, *Jataragni dipti*, *Chirat ca pakam vayasah*.^[30]

To achieve these desired outcomes, the procedure must be undertaken with careful consideration-this involves proper assessment of *Koshta* for *Snehapana*, accurate calculation of the *Virechana* dose, appropriate selection of the purification procedure and judicious choice of medicines.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the assessment of *Koshta* is a keystone in the judicious administration of *Virechana* karma. Its evaluation enables practitioners to fix purgative doses according to patient's bowel nature ensuring both therapeutic efficacy and safety. This evaluation not only guides the selection of appropriate *Shodhana* methods like *Virechana*, *Basti*, or *Snehapana*, but also informs the choice of medicines, their dosage, and the timing of administration. Integration of this classical concept into practice not only preserves the essence of traditional wisdom but also advances the standards of personalized care in *Shodhana* therapies.

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